

Life of a specialised and a non-specialised carnivore: Comparative behaviour and functional morphology of two species of terrestrial molluscs (Gastropoda: Rhytididae) in South Africa

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ABSTRACT

Behaviour of two southern African endemics from the family Rhytididae, *Chlamydephorus burnupi* (E.A. Smith, 1892) and *Nata vernicosa* (Krauss, 1848), is observed and discussed. The sophisticated hunting behaviour of the African Rhytididae has likely evolved from an opportunistic carrion diet, as well as consumption of earthworms that surfaced after the rain, followed by specialisation in preying on slugs and snails. *Nata vernicosa*, one of the smaller shelled rhytidids, demonstrates feeding flexibility by consuming any snail that it is capable of killing, as well as carrion every time it is found. Evolution of highly specialised feeding behaviour of *C. burnupi* that feeds exclusively on smooth pill-millipedes from the genus *Sphaerotherium* Brandt, 1833 (Oniscomorpha, Diplopoda), resulted in the largest pedal gland in the genus that contains a significant volume of toxic mucus, specialised radula capable of breaking through the ventral exoskeleton of a millipede, and a unique body shape that allows *C. burnupi* to spend most of its time resting on any side in a curled position, thus decreasing evaporation and presenting a stronger challenge to predators.

KEYWORDS: Gastropoda, *Chlamydephorus*, *Nata*, carnivore, behaviour, evolution, functional morphology.

INTRODUCTION

The vast majority of terrestrial molluscs, contrary to a popular belief, are not herbivores (herbivores feed on autotrophs). Their initial way of consumption most likely was mycophagy (through detritophagy), as terrestrial molluscs generally do not feed on bryophytes (mosses in a broad sense), lycophytes (clubmosses and related taxa), polypodiophytes (ferns) and gymnosperms. Those molluscs that feed on angiosperms often prefer plant parts damaged by fungi (Simroth 1901: 112). Many molluscs that are capable of consuming plant material still have a preference for fungi (Fig. 1, and numerous personal observations on other Agriolimacidae that consume mushrooms), some herbivores readily feast on carrion (Ingram 1941: 649) and others feed almost exclusively on carrion when they are young (Fig. 2). All that leads to the conclusion that consumption of animals by terrestrial molluscs evolved not from herbivory, but (through carrion consumption) from mycophagy (Simroth 1901: 112).

Barker and Efford (2004) summarised the prior knowledge on predatory terrestrial gastropods and found that they primarily feed on other gastropods and earthworms (2004: 365). Understandably, “most arthropods move too quickly and are too well protected by their chitinous exoskeleton to fall prey to snails” Watson (1915: 225). There are, however, arthropods that rely on the protection of their exoskeleton to such an extent, that they typically would not try to escape when attacked: pill-isopods (Armadillidiidae Brandt, 1833) and pill-millipedes (Oniscomorpha Pocock,

1887). Instead, they roll into a ‘ball’ (conglobation) and wait for an attacker to leave. Three species of carnivorous slugs of the genus *Chlamydephorus* W.G. Binney, 1879 exploited that defensive behaviour and started to feed on some species of the genus *Sphaerotherium* Brandt, 1833 (Diplopoda) in South Africa (Herbert 2000).

Terrestrial slugs of the genus *Chlamydephorus* are well known despite the relative rarity of most of them. These remarkable animals are autochthons of Southern Africa and inhabit forested coastal areas from Cape Town to the border with Mozambique, as well as the slopes of the Great Escarpment (mostly Drakensberg), with one species in the easternmost part of Zimbabwe.

A comprehensive historical overview of all studies on the species of the genus *Chlamydephorus* described prior to 1915 and the detailed description of their external and internal morphology, as well as the description of three new species, were published by Hugh Watson in October 1915 (Watson 1915). It remains the best reference for further information on the genus.

Their shelled relatives from the genus *Nata* H. Watson, 1934 are also carnivores, but they are relatively common and were recently well revised by Herbert and Moussalli (2016).

The currently used system (Tillier 1989: 72; Bouchet *et al.* 2017: 362), based on morphological (Watson 1915; Tillier 1989) and molecular (Wade *et al.* 2001:

Figures 1, 2: (1) *Deroceras caucasicum* (Simroth, 1901) burrowing into *Boletus edulis* (Bulliard) on Northern Caucasus; (2) juveniles of *Euonyma natalensis* (Burnup, 1905) cleaning the remains of *Sphaerotherium hanstroemi* Schubart, 1958.

416, 2006: 600; Herbert & Mitchell 2009: 213, 218; Herbert *et al.* 2015: 266; Moussalli & Herbert 2016: 105; Teasdale 2017: 155) evidence, places both *Chlamydephorus* and *Nata* into Rhytididae:

Class Gastropoda Cuvier, 1795

Order Stylommatophora A. Schmidt, 1855

Superfamily Rhytidoidea Pilsbry, 1893

Family Rhytididae Pilsbry, 1893

Subfamily Rhytidinae Pilsbry, 1893

Type genus: *Rhytida* Albers, 1860 (in Albers & Martens, 1860: 89).

Genus *Nata* H. Watson, 1934

Nata H. Watson, 1934: 158; Connolly 1939: 98, 99; Wenz in Wenz & Zilch 1960: 553; Richardson 1989: 45; Schileyko 2000: 747; Herbert & Kilburn 2004: 218; Herbert & Moussalli 2016: 18. (Type species: *Natalina tarachodes* Connolly, 1912: 96, by orig. des.)

Subfamily Chlamydephorinae Cockerell, 1935

Chlamydephoridae Cockerell, 1935: 143. (Type genus: *Chlamydephorus* W.G. Binney, 1879: 331.)

Not Chlamidophorina C.L. Bonaparte, 1851 [1850]: 476. (Type genus: *Chlamyphorus* Harlan, 1825 (Mammalia: Dasyopodidae).)

Aperidae Möllendorff, 1903 [1902]: 5; Connolly 1912: 62, 1939: i, 6; Thiele 1931: 726. (Type genus: *Apera* Heynemann, 1885: 20.)

Aperidae Collinge, 1910: 159, 163. (Type genus: *Apera* Heynemann, 1885: 20.)

Genus *Chlamydephorus* W.G. Binney, 1879

Chlamydephorus W.G. Binney, 1879: 331; Fischer 1880: 368, 369; Dall 1880: 430; Kobelt 1881: 91, 92; Martens 1881: 65, 66; Binney 1884: 81, 136; Tryon 1885: 7, 17; Cockerell 1890: 390, 1935: 142; Cockerell & Collinge 1893: 189, 206; Cooke 1895: 334, 440; Simroth 1896: 5, 19, 20; Sarasin & Sarasin 1899: 106, 112; Wenz in Wenz & Zilch 1960: 555; Boss 1982: 1072; Richardson 1989: 2, 12; Rosenberg 1989: 153; Herbert 1997: 209, 2000: 4; Schileyko 2000: 753; Herbert & Kilburn 2004: 285. (Type species: *Chlamydephorus gibbonsi* W.G. Binney, 1879: 331.)

Chlamydephorus: Tryon 1884: 13, 366; Fischer 1887: 448, 449; Simroth 1901: 110, 111.

Apera Heynemann, 1885: 20, 1905: 23; Smith 1892: 465;

Cooke 1895: 334, 440; Collinge 1897: 221, 1900, 1901a, 1901b, 1910: 159, 163; Simroth 1901: 110 *et seq.*; Möllendorff 1903: 5; Pilsbry 1907: xi; Connolly 1912: 62, 1939: 6; Watson 1915: 107 *et seq.*; Thiele 1931: 727). (Type species: *Chlamydephorus gibbonsi* W.G. Binney, 1879: 331.)

Not *Chlamydephorus* Lenz, 1831: xi [“*Chlamyphorus* (richtiger wäre *Chlamydephorus* oder *Chlamydephorus*)”].

Not *Chlamyphorus* Harlan, 1825a: 236–246, 1825b: 154–163; Lenz 1831: xi, 217, 310. (Mammalia: Dasyopodidae)

There have been few occasional direct observations of the feeding behaviour of chlamydephorid slugs. Watson (1915: 158) mentioned that *C. gibbonsi* W.G. Binney, 1879: 331 feeds on earthworms and Pieterse *et al.* (2017) described how this slug fed on earthworms in captivity. Forcart (1967: 520) mentioned in his description of *C. bruggeni* that holotype of that species “found devouring a *Sphaerotherium* spec. (Diplopoda)”. Herbert (1997: 209) reported *C. dimidius* (H. Watson, 1915: 204) eating a small specimen of *Trachycystis* in captivity. Three years later, Herbert (2000) presented results of his detailed observations of *C. sexangulus* (H. Watson, 1915: 213) consuming pill-millipedes of the genus *Sphaerotherium* and mentioned that he personally observed *C. burnupi* (E.A. Smith, 1892) feeding on *Sphaerotherium* as well (Herbert 2000: 4). All historical knowledge related to the feeding behaviour of *Chlamydephorus* was summarised by Herbert and Kilburn (2004: 285–289).

The results of observations on the feeding, as well as on the general behaviour of two species of Rhytididae, *Chlamydephorus burnupi* and *Nata vernicosa* (Krauss, 1848), are presented below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Chlamydephorus burnupi (Figs 3–5) is a rare species that inhabits humid forests, as well as thick grass and bracken (Herbert & Kilburn 2004: 287) almost exclusively in the KwaZulu-Natal province of South Africa. The KwaZulu-Natal Museum collection con-

Figures 3–5: *Chlamydephorus burnupi* (E.A. Smith, 1892): (3) actively crawling; (4) inactive; (5A, 5B) resting in defensive positions.

tains only 13 records (1903–2004) and nine observations (1974–2022) of this species from the eastern part of the Great Escarpment, as well as from the forested slopes of smaller escarpments half way down

from the Drakensberg to the Indian Ocean coast. Two extreme records (Port St Johns on the Wild Coast in Eastern Cape in 1946, and the White River area in Mpumalanga in the northern part of the Great Escarpment in 1974) suggest a wider distribution of *C. burnupi* in interglacial periods of the Pleistocene.

Nata vernicosa is a common species that dwells in wide varieties of habitats. The Mollusca Collection of the KwaZulu-Natal Museum alone contains 477 records (1905–2023) of this species from Cape Town to southern Mozambique, and from the coastal areas of the Indian Ocean up to Lesotho. The taxonomy of *N. vernicosa* is comprehensively covered by Herbert and Moussalli (2016).

One specimen of *C. burnupi*, collected on 17 October 2022 in the Monk's Cowl Nature Reserve in the Drakensberg, and one specimen of *N. vernicosa*, collected on 13 June 2023 in the Ferncliff Nature Reserve in Pietermaritzburg, were kept alive in a terrarium with the soil and leaf litter from their original localities. Observations and photographs on the feeding and overall behaviour of both animals were made till February 2024, when they were released back to their original localities.

Both species co-occur in the Ferncliff Nature Reserve and, because of that, invertebrates that were given them for feeding, were collected from that locality. Those various invertebrates included termites, earthworms, terrestrial snails and slugs (both native and introduced), terrestrial amphipods (Talitridae), pill-isopods (Armadillidiidae), flat-backed millipedes (Polydesmida) and three species of pill-millipedes (Oniscomorpha). Small pieces of springbok antelope (*Antidorcas marsupialis* (Zimmermann, 1780)) meat were given to both animals as well.

Pill-millipedes were identified using the revision of Oniscomorpha by Schubart (1958) and the partial revision of the South African species by Spiegel *et al.* (2002). All the references to the presence of *Sphaerotherium rotundatum* Brandt, 1833 in KwaZulu-Natal should be verified based on the re-examination of the structure of the endotergum (the underside of the posterior tergal margin).

RESULTS

The specimen of *C. burnupi* (Fig. 3), reaching the maximum length of 170 mm when completely extended, was noticeably inactive most of the time (Fig. 4) that confirms observation of that species behaviour by Herbert and Kilburn (2004: 287). The animal regularly rested for many hours on its side and even upside-down, only occasionally trying to burrow into the leaf litter (Fig. 5). It lived for 16

Figure 6: *Chlamydephorus burnupi* (E.A. Smith, 1892) feeding on *Sphaerotherium giganteum* Porath, 1872.

Figure 7: *Chlamydephorus burnupi* (E.A. Smith, 1892) feeding on *Sphaerotherium hanstroemi* Schubart, 1958.

Figure 8: Pill-isopods Armadillidiidae next to *Chlamydephorus burnupi* with no harm to any of them.

months in captivity and consumed six pill-millipedes in total: three juveniles of *Sphaerotherium giganteum* Porath, 1872 (Fig. 6) and three adults of *S. hanstroemi* Schubart, 1958 (Fig. 7). All various invertebrates (see above), as well as carrion, presented as potential food sources, were ignored. Pill-isopods often preferred to rest next to *C. burnupi* without any harm to both species (Fig. 8). Another millipede of the same genus, *S. dorsale* (Gervais, 1847), was ignored by *C. burnupi* after an initial attempt to attack it (Fig. 9) and they lived together one month after that in the same terrarium. One polydesmid millipede (Fig. 10) was ignored, but died within four hours after coming in contact with the mucus of *C. burnupi*, was not eaten by the slug and consumed later by juveniles of *Euonyma natalensis* (Burnup, 1905).

The specimen of *N. vernicosa* exhibited territorial behaviour, normally returning to the same hiding place after a successful or unsuccessful hunt, changing its preferred hiding place every few days. It regularly fed on juveniles of an introduced snail *Cornu aspersum* (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Fig. 11) and on adults of the native tail-wagger *Kerkophorus poeppigii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Fig. 12), carrying the retracted into the shell prey to the hiding place and finishing consuming it there (Fig. 11). *Nata vernicosa* enthusiastically devoured carrion every time it was available (Fig. 13).

DISCUSSION

A number of additional observations, made during this study, have allowed some conclusions to be made on the functional morphology and on the evolution of *Chlamydephorus* behaviour.

Figures 9, 10: *Chlamydephorus burnupi* (9) trying to attack *Sphaerotherium dorsale* Porath, 1872, and (10) ignoring a polydesmid millipede trying to hide under the slug.

Burnup informed his nephew Watson (1915: 115), that *Chlamydephorus gibbonsi* “much resemble the rhizomes of ferns” in their resting position. Watson (1915: 122) also mentioned that “the chestnut-brown colour of *A. burnupi* may help to render the slug inconspicuous among dead leaves”. Indeed, *Chlamydephorus burnupi* often lives in the forest with a significant presence of the South African evergreen endemic tree *Leucosidea sericea* Ecklon & Zeyher (Rosaceae), and the studied animal was collected in the leaf litter that largely consisted of *L. sericea* foliage. The posterior part of *Chlamydephorus burnupi* has remarkable resemblance with the leaves of *L. sericea* (Fig. 14), and is difficult to notice when *Chlamydephorus burnupi* burrows into the leaf litter leaving posterior end with pneumostome on the surface (Fig. 15). The distribution of *C. burnupi* is well within the distribution of *L. sericea* (Ranwashe 2022), and the slug’s resem-

Figure 11: *Nata vernicosa* (Krauss, 1848) feeding on a juvenile specimen of the introduced *Cornu aspersum* (O.F. Müller, 1774).

blance suggests mimicry that may decrease predation by reptiles, birds and small mammals.

Collinge (1910: 168) mentioned that Burnup, who had sent him a series of *C. burnupi* illustrations, noticed that this species “curls itself up”. This resting behaviour obviously became possible only after the pneumostome had attained its current medial position, and the observations presented here indicate that it is, almost certainly, a result of the hunting behaviour. Herbert (1997: 209, fig. 26) described and illustrated similar defensive position of *C. gibbonsi*, but this species has a more or less cylindrical body shape and is not as efficient at that as *C. burnupi* (Figs 5–7). The presence of longitudinal keels in *C. burnupi* and *C. sexangulus* do not “possibly serve to increase the rigidity of the skin” (Watson 1915: 116), but are an adaptation to kill pill-millipedes more efficiently by enveloping prey and thus not allowing it to escape (Figs 6, 7). Both *C. burnupi* and *C. sexangulus* share not only a similar body shape, but a similar radula as well (Watson 1915: 157–163) and are closely related based on morphological (Watson 1915: 217) and molecular evidence (Moussalli & Herbert 2016: 105). Watson (1915: 163) suggested that radula similarities in these two species resulted from their living “chiefly on some special kind of

food, and have their radulae specially modified in consequence”. Indeed, both species are specialised to prey on pill-millipedes and probably evolved from a common ancestor (Herbert 2000: 4).

The initial stage of the hunt normally starts when a pill-millipede comes in contact with the slug or when the slug detects the millipede movement within a short range (less than five centimetres) of its central or peripheral view. In most cases, the slug is not actively hunting. This suggests that *C. burnupi* is probably using the same hiding places as its prey in the natural environment. However, despite this narrow specialisation in preying only on certain species of pill-millipedes, *C. burnupi* is not always successful in killing and eating its prey. Pill-millipedes are always trying to escape after their initial contact with the slug, violently opening and closing the ‘ball of the body’ and crawling away. And even if a pill-millipede has been initially paralysed by the slug’s mucus, it often recovers and moves away. Most of the failed cases result from premature attempts of the slug to consume the pill-millipede. An incompletely paralysed millipede often successfully defends itself by flailing its legs that irritate tentacles of the slug, leading to the prompt release of its prey, regardless of its size.

Figures 12, 13: (12) *Nata vernicosa* consuming an adult of native *Kerkophorus poeppigii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846); (13) an adult and two juveniles of *N. vernicosa* devouring springbok meat, the consumed meat is visible through the shell.

Following the successful kill of a pill-millipede by enveloping it and thus not allowing the prey to escape, the slug proceeds to consuming the inside matter of the millipede within 14 hours through a small opening, which the slug typically makes under the prey's head. The slug retracts its optical tentacles during this stage, and readily devours the millipede at a steady rate, extricating itself from the corpse of the millipede only to re-enter through a different section of the ventral exoskeleton often tearing it apart as a result.

The death of one polydesmid millipede shortly after coming in contact with the skin of *C. burnupi* suggests that any mucus of the slug has a toxin that paralyzes and kills these arthropods. However, it is confirmed in this study that the main source of the mucus with the toxin that paralyzes millipedes is excreted by the pedal gland (Herbert 2000: 4).

Besides active defence strategies, one species of pill-millipedes in this study has been found defending

Figures 14, 15: (14) Leaves of *Leucosidea sericea* Ecklon & Zeyher, the South African endemic evergreen tree; (15) *Chlamydephorus burnupi* burrowing into leaf litter with the significant presence of the *L. sericea* dead foliage from the original locality in Drakensberg.

passively. Dense hair that covers all tergites of *S. dorsale* (Fig. 9) successfully repels the mucus of *C. burnupi*, not allowing it to come in contact with the surface of the tergites. This is another remarkable example of 'a spear and a shield' co-evolution.

The complex hunting behaviour of the African Rhytididae has likely evolved from an opportunistic carrion consumption (Fig. 13), as well as consumption of earthworms that surfaced after the rain, followed by specialisation in preying on slugs and snails. Herbert & Moussalli (2010: 7–9) summarised all known observation on the diet of the shelled South African Rhytididae. Some species have developed sophisticated techniques to consume a hunted prey more efficiently by carrying the killed snails into hiding places (Fig. 11). The calcium carbonate content of the shell is subsequently gradually dissolved and absorbed (Appleton & Heeg 1999; Barker & Efford 2004; Herbert & Kilburn 2004; Herbert & Moussalli 2010). For example, *Natalina cafra* (A. Férussac, 1821) can keep a number of shells in different stages

of dissolution of their calcium carbonate content in a hiding place where it returns after a hunt (pers. obs.), similarly to *Nata vernicosa*.

Different species of *Chlamydephorus* demonstrate different ways of specialization of their feeding preferences and behaviour. Less specialised species consume earthworms, slugs and snails much like their shelled relatives. Species that started to specialise on feeding on pill-millipedes, particularly the closely related *C. burnupi* and *C. sexangulus*, evolved morphological structures that allow them to break the defence of their prey more efficiently.

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